

A New Instrument (Scale) for Measuring the Socio -Economic Status of Urban and Rural Communities in India: Preliminary Study

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Abstract

Background and Objective: Socio economic status (SES) is one of the most important variables in social science studies/researches. Society is not static, social class changes over the time with changing concepts of SES. So there is a continuous need to develop a quite reliable, valid and applicable SES scale. With the continuous and fast changes in the structure of the society regular changes in the scale is required to suit the present condition, therefore, the present efforts are being made to prepare a reliable and valid socio economic status scale to suit in the present senior. The present scale is applicable both for urban as well as rural families.

Methodology: A community based study was carried out on 120 families of rural and slum areas of Uttar Pradesh. The proposed SES scale is having 21 variables. Reliability was tested on 60 families and applicability and validity was tested on 120 families. Data collected was analyzed and inferred with correlation test.

Result: In the present study the result shows that out of the 120 families only 3 families (2.5%) belonged to high socio economic status, while 10 families(8.33%), 13 families(10.83%) and 29 families (24.17%) belonged to upper middle, middle and lower middle socio economic status respectively. The result further shows that most of the families [45 families (37.5%)] belonged to poor socio economic status while 20 families (16.67%) belonged to very poor socio economic status.

Reliability ($r=0.93$) and validity of the proposed SES was found very high in the present study.

Conclusion: The proposed SES scale includes the majority of the determinants of social class in a composite subjective manner. Applicability, Reliability and validity of the proposed SES were found very high. Proposed SES scale is able to discriminate families between different socio-economic statuses. So this proposed scale is fit to use in community based study.

Key Words: socio economic status, Reliability, Validity, Applicability

INTRODUCTION

It is essential to understand the Socio Economic Status (SES) of the community in order to correlate its impact on health and quality of living standards. Almost all community based studies focus on socio economic stratification, which is the key parameter for proper understanding the affordability of the community of health services, amenities and their purchasing capacity. It plays a significant role in planning and execution of developmental programmes.

Socio economic status (SES) is a measure of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others. Various variables are responsible for that like income, education, occupation, family effluence, physical assets, social position, social participation, caste, political influence, etc. Majority of researchers agree that income, education and occupation together best represent SES, while some others feel that changes in family structure, family effluence etc should also be considered. Wealth is also considered a determinant of SES, which is a set of economic reserves or assets, presents a source of security providing a measure of a household's ability to meet emergencies, absorb economic shocks, or provide the means to live comfortably. Wealth reflects intergenerational transitions as well as accumulation of income and savings.

SES influences on the incidence and prevalence of various health related conditions. Socio Economic Status also influences social security in terms of the accessibility, affordability, acceptability and actual utilization of various health facilities.

Several experts recommended different scales to measure the Socio Economic Status in both rural and urban areas. These are:-

Socio Economic Status Scale for Urban Areas

- **Prasad's socio economic status classification (1961)** Prasad's classification based on the per capita monthly income and later modified in 1968 and 1970 has been extensively used in India.
- **Kumar (1993-94)** Kumar modified the Prasad's socio economic status classification due to the inflationary trend in economy in 1993-94. An attempt has been made to link it with the all India consumer price index (AICPI) and a modified classification has been proposed with a built in provision of its upgrading from time to time.
- **Kuppuswami socio economic status scale (1976)** Kuppuswami socio economic status scale is widely used to measure the socio economic status of an individual in urban communities. It is based on three variables namely education, occupation and income. Letter on modification of Kuppuswami scale were done, where the education and occupation of head of the family and income per capita per month was used.
- **Mishra et al (2003) and Kumar et al (2007)** they suggested an economic revision of Kuppuswami scale because changes in inflation rate change the monetary values of the monthly income range scores.
- **Bairwa et al (2012)** they linked the income limits of the Kuppuswami socio economic scale with CPI and revised the scale.

Socio Economic Status Scale for Rural Areas

- **Pareekh's socio economic status classification (1964)** Pareekh's classification became popular based on nine characteristics namely caste, occupation of family head, education of family head, level of social participation of family head, landholding, housing, farm power, material possessions and type of family.
- **Rahudkar (1960) and Shirpurkar (1964)** also developed the scale for assessing the socio economic status of farm families.

Socio Economic Status Scale for Both Rural and Slum Areas

- **Agrawal et al (2005)** scale is questionnaire based, has 22 questions regarding various indicators of SES.
- **Tiwari et al (2005)** in this scale seven indicators namely housing, material possession, education, occupation, monthly income, land and social participation, has been used for accessing the socio economic status.
- **Gaur K.L. (2013)** this scale also has seven indicators namely education, occupation, income per capita, expenditure, housing condition, living status and debt to assets ratio.

Likewise, there are many SES scales, some are suitable for rural community but not for urban, some had considered limited determinants of SES and few considered a number of similar determinants several times.

Socio economic status (SES) is one of the most important variables in social science studies/researches. So there is a continuous need to develop a quite reliable, valid and applicable SES scale. With the continuous and fast changes in the structure of the society regular changes in the scale is required to suit the present condition, therefore, the present efforts are being made to prepare a reliable and valid socio economic status scale to suit in the present senior. The present scale is being developed to measure the socio economic status of the individual or family enlisting the majority of measurement of socio economic status of present era in a complied scientific manner. Furthermore, here the researcher tried to make more objective SES scale, which can be used for all sections of the society. The present scale is applicable both for urban as well as rural families.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A new scale for measuring the socio economic status of rural as well as urban community was developed by the authors, based on literature review, available scale and extensive discussion with sociologists, economists and public health experts.

For formulating the scale at initial stage, 17 variables of socio economic status were listed with the help of available scales. These were:-

1. Caste,
2. Education of head of the family,
3. Occupation of head of the family,
4. Income of family,
5. Type of family,
6. Size of family,
7. Number of children of the family,
8. Education of children of the family,
9. Family educational status,
10. Possession of agricultural land (only for rural areas),
11. Possession of non-agricultural land,
12. Presence of milch and non milch cattle for business purpose,

13. Types of house ownership,
14. Types of house,
15. Material Possession such as equipment, vehicles, furniture, kitchen appliances & utensils etc.
16. Possession of agriculture equipment (only for rural areas) and
17. Social participation of head of the family,

The prepared list of SES variables was submitted to experts to give their expert advice in regards of selected variables in the present context. Although it was approved by public health experts, sociologists and economist with some minor modification.

But there were suggestion on some more/other variables to be including in the present SES scale to determining the socio economic status of various communities more scientifically. These were:-

1. Income expenditure pattern,
2. Besides the house in which the family is living any other property as house and shop,
3. Water facilities and
4. Electricity facility.

Thus the revised draft of scale had total 21 variables for deciding the SES, out of which 2 variables (Possession of agricultural land and Possession of agriculture equipment) are applied only for rural area, while rest of the other variables are applied for both rural as well as urban areas.

With every variable, suitable alternatives were added and suitable weighted score was given to each alternative and then resubmitted to experts. Many alternatives, which were not approved by the experts or found to be insignificant in measuring the SES, were subsequently discarded. The weighted score for every alternative of the profile was determined on the basis of recommendation given by the experts and the experience of the researcher. Although in regards of weighted score of each alternative of selected variables, prepared SES scale was approved by expert but some major modification in weighted score of the profile of 'social participation of head of the family' and 'equipment and vehicles possession' were suggested by the expert. These were:-

PREDRAFT OF THE SCALE			REVISED DRAFT OF THE SCALE	
Profile	Alternatives	Score	Alternatives	Score
Social Participation of Head of the Family	• Post held in each organization	2 score	• Post held in each organization • Membership for each organization	2 score (max 6 score)**
	• Membership for each organization	1 score		1 score (max 3 score) **
Equipments and Vehicles Possession	• Modern equipments and vehicles	2 score	• Very modern and luxurious equipments and vehicles	3 score
	• Traditional equipments	1 score		

	and vehicles		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modern equipments and vehicles • Traditional equipments and vehicles 	2 score 1 score
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**Expert suggested that the obtained total score of social participation profile was very comprehensive, although it should have a maximum value for calculating the total socio economic status scores.

This revised draft of the scale was administered on 30 families selected on random basis, 15 families from urban areas and 15 families from rural areas of Agra district. In course of administration of the scale, it was found that the range of the land area in house profile was not appropriate; therefore, in final draft it was expanded. Moreover, the alternatives in the house type of the same profile were also redefined in the final draft. In the sub-section of the equipment possession profile, some more household gadgets, which reflect SES, were added.

The final draft

Thus the final draft of scale had total 21 variables for deciding the SES (Annexure -1). Suitable weighted was given to each variable and scoring for each variable was based on a scale ranging from 2 to 9, i.e. variable 06 regarding the types of family was scaled on a 2 point scale and variable 02 regarding education of head of the family was scaled on a 9 point scale. The maximum aggregate score was 72 for urban areas and 79 for rural areas. Based on the final score, the socio-economic status of the family is divided into six socio-economic categories. These were:-

S.NO.	CATEGORIES	SCORE	
		[for rural areas]	[for urban areas]
1	High socio economic status	combined score more than 65	combined score more than 60
2	Upper middle socio economic status	52 – 64	48 – 59
3	Middle socio economic status	39 – 51	36 – 47
4	Lower middle socio economic status	26 – 38	24 – 35
5	Poor socio economic status	13 – 25	12 – 23
6	Very poor socio economic status	combined score less than 13	combined score less than 12

The final draft of the scale was again sent to experts through author's network and personal. All the experts were of the opinion that the scale was a useful instrument according to current need. Useful suggestions were incorporated and necessary modifications were done in the final draft to make it culture-free, standard and countrywide applicable scale both in urban and rural areas. After all these exercises, the final version of the scale was developed.

Administration of the final draft:

For administration of the final draft of the scale two districts of Uttar Pradesh namely 'Agra district' and 'Mainpuri district' were selected. Out of these two districts 60 families from rural areas (30 families from each selected rural area of each district) and 60 families from urban areas (30 families from each selected urban area of each district) selected on random basis. Thus the present study was conducted among total 120 families (60 from rural areas and 60 from urban areas) of Uttar Pradesh. The participants expressed their willingness to co-operate with the study which was done with the following objective:-

- To assess the validity of the contents and elements of items in each of the twenty variable of the scale.
- To assess its applicability among the selected families
- To assess the reliability by re-administering the scale on the same families after a gap of one month.

Testing of the final draft:

Adequate questionnaire/scale construction is crucial. A useful method for checking a questionnaire/scale and making sure whether it is accurately capturing the intended information is to pretest the 'reliability' and 'validity' of the questionnaire/scale. So, this proposed SES scale was tested in terms of reliability and validity.

Reliability

The reliability of the scale was determined by test-retest method. This proposed SES scale was administered to a sample of 60 families (30 from rural areas and 30 from urban areas) and compiling their respective scores. After one month, it was again re-administered on the same sample and scores are noted. The two series of scores are arranged pair-wise, a pair being the scores of the candidate in two repetition of the test. Karl- Pearson's coefficient of co-relation between the two series is taken as the measurement of reliability.

The administration and re-administration of the final draft of SES scale on rural and urban families of Uttar Pradesh resulted in necessitating no changes in the basic structure of the scale. It only required some additions in the contents/elements of the specific profiles of the scale. These contents/elements had local relevance.

Validity

The content and concurrent validity was tested of proposed SES scale. The content validity was tested by opinion of subject experts.

The concurrent validity was tested on the final draft. The usual way of testing concurrent validity is by finding out how well scores correspond to some outside criterion of variable being measured. The relationship of the scale scores with identifiable groups (known groups) was used as the criterion for this purpose.

For testing the concurrent validity, three resource persons who knew very well about their locality and population, were individually explained the exercise and requested to identify families in their locality who, as per their discretion and judgment, belonged to high, upper-middle, middle, lower-middle poor and very poor socioeconomic status. Out of a total of 120

families there was a total agreement between the resource persons in respect of the SES category to which 92 (60 from rural and 32 from urban) families belonged. Among 28 families where the opinions differed about the SES category of the families, the difference was of only one class (up or down). When the developed scale was applied on these 92 families, it classified all but four families in the category to which they were classified by resource persons. The four families with disagreement were classified as belonging to middle SES class by the scale, while two each were classified as belonging to upper middle and lower-middle classes by the resource persons. These findings showed very high validity of the scale, demonstrating its sensitivity to discriminate families between upper middle, middle and lower middle classes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed SES scale includes the following 20 variables:-

1. Caste,
2. Education of head of the family,
3. Occupation of head of the family,
4. Income of family,
5. Income expenditure pattern,
6. Type of family,
7. Size of family
8. Number of children of the family,
9. Education of children of the family,
10. Family educational status,
11. Possession of agricultural land (only for rural areas),
12. Possession of non-agricultural land,
13. Presence of milch and non milch cattle for business purpose,
14. Types of house ownership,
15. Types of house,
16. Besides the house in which the family is living any other property as house and shop,
17. Water facilities,
18. Electricity facility,
19. Material Possession such as equipment, vehicles, furniture, kitchen appliances & utensils etc.,
20. Possession of agriculture equipment (only for rural areas) and
21. Social participation of head of the family.

For determining the reliabilities of the proposed SES scale it was administered to 60 families (30 from rural areas and 30 from urban areas) and for validity it was administered to 120 families (60 from rural areas and 60 from urban areas) of Uttar Pradesh identified on stratified random sample.

In the present study, reliability for the proposed SES scale was observed very high ($r=0.92$) by test re-test method done on 60 families. Almost similar observations were of other authors like Pareek's, Gaur, K.L.'s, Agarwal et al's SES scale etc.

There was a total agreement between the resource persons in respect of the concurrent validity of the proposed SES in the present study.

According to this SES scale out of the 120 families only 3 families (2.5%) belonged to high socio economic status, while 10 families(8.33%), 13 families(10.83%) and 29 families (24.17%) belonged to upper middle, middle and lower middle socio economic status respectively. The result further shows that most of the families [45 (37.5%)] belonged to poor socio economic status and only 20 families (16.67%) belonged to very poor socio economic status.

CONCLUSION

The proposed SES scale includes majority of the determinants of social class in a composite subjective manner. Applicability, Reliability and Validity of the proposed SES was found very high in the present study. So this proposed scale is fit to use in community based study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Since this type of instrument has been developed first time, the reliability and external validity of this scale need to be tested prior to its acceptance. Hence, it is recommended that other researcher should test it in their urban and rural field practice areas.

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